

Screening of Phytochemicals and Estimation of Secondary Metabolites in Plant Species *Euphorbia neriifolia* L. and *Caralluma fimbriata* Wall.

Bharat Hajgude & Ravi P. Patil.

Department of Botany, Deogiri College, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar- 431005.

Corresponding Author – Bharat Hajgude

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Abstract:

The active components that give medicinal plants their therapeutic properties are phytochemicals, which are usually secondary metabolites like alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and tannins. Portions of the therapeutic herbs *Caralluma fimbriata* and *Euphorbia neriifolia* were investigated for secondary metabolites. Different techniques were used to estimate each secondary metabolite, such as the aluminium chloride colorimetric method for flavonoids, the Folin-Ciocalteu method for phenol, and the Folin-Denis method for tannin. *Euphorbia neriifolia* has the highest levels of flavonoids, tannin, and phenol. *Caralluma fimbriata* on the other hand, had a lower phenol content. It will be necessary to employ robust analytical separation and detection techniques like GCMS and HR-LCMS in future studies on secondary metabolites.

Keywords: *Caralluma fimbriata*, Folin-Denis, tannin, *Euphorbia neriifolia*. GCMS and HR-LCMS

Introduction:

The many secondary metabolites of *C. fimbriata*, such as steroidal glycosides, alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, and tannins, are responsible for its pharmacological characteristics (Barthwal R & Mahar R 2024). It is commonly known to relieve thirst and control obesity in ethnic groups and has been used historically as a vegetable (Malladi S et al.2018). The medicinal properties of *Euphorbia neriifolia*, including its antiviral, anticonvulsant, radioprotective, anti-arthritic, anti-asthmatic, anti-fertility, anti-diarrheal, and anti-ulcer properties, are well documented.(M.Hasan et al.2014)

Materials and Methods:

The chosen plant species were collected at random from different localities of Marathwada

Plant Extraction: Using an electronic blender, 50 g of each of the plants *Euphorbia neriifolia* and *Caralluma fimbriata* were ground into a fine

powder. For efficient extraction, the ground plant material was subsequently put through a Soxhlet extraction process in the lab. The filtrates were saved for additional examination and the resultant crude extracts were utilised for quantitative estimation.

Phytochemical studies:

Tannin Content Determination: Folin-Denis method was used for determination of tannin content. (Ram and Malhotra, 1993; Sane, 2002)

Materials:

Folin-Denis Reagent, Sodium Carbonate Solution, Standard Tannic Acid Solution, Working Standard Solution.

Procedure: 0.5 g of plant material is boiled, centrifuged, and 1 ml of the extract is reacted with sodium carbonate and Folin-Denis reagent to extract and quantify tannin. A tannic acid standard curve is used to calculate the concentration after the resultant blue colour is detected at 700 nm.

Phenol Content Determination: The Singleton and Rossi (1965) method was used to measure the phenol content. Mix the sample and Folin reagent (1:1), adding 1 ml Na₂CO₃, and diluting to 10 ml and incubate for 3 minutes, after 90 minutes in the dark, measure the absorbance at 650 nm.

Flavonoid Content Determination: The aluminium chloride colorimetric method was used

to determine the flavonoid concentration. Total Flavonoid Content is determined using the Aluminium Chloride Colorimetric Assay, in which AlCl₃ forms a coloured complex with flavonoids that are detected at 430 nm and quantified against a Rutin standard curve.

Observation tables:

Sr. No	Plant species	Flavonoids	Phenols	Tannins
1	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i>	+	+	+
2	<i>Caralluma fimbriata</i>	+	+	+

Table No.1: Phytochemical Screening of Medicinal Plant

Estimation of Phenol

Standard conc.mg/ml	O.D of Standard Solution at 760nm
0.1	0.062
0.2	0.087
0.3	0.120
0.4	0.202
0.5	0.285
0.6	0.324
0.7	0.350
0.8	0.370
0.9	0.430
1.0	0.502

Sample	O.D at 730 nm
<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i>	2.000
<i>Caralluma fimbriata</i>	1.246

Estimation of Tannins

Standard conc.mg/ml	O.D of Standard Solution at 500nm
0.1	0.004
0.2	0.007
0.3	0.007
0.4	0.008
0.5	0.009
0.6	0.010
0.7	0.012
0.8	0.014
0.9	0.015
1.0	0.016

Sample	O.D at 500 nm
<i>Euphorbia neriifolia.</i>	0.129
<i>Caralluma fimbriata</i>	0.065

O.D of Standard Solution at 760nm

O.D of Standard Solution at 500nm

Estimation of Flavonoids

Standard conc. mg/ml	O.D of Standard Solution at 500nm	O.D of Standard Solution at 500nm
0.1	0.763	0.085
0.2	0.830	0.131
0.3	1.011	0.262
0.4	1.613	0.404
0.5	2.000	0.462
0.6	2.000	0.487
0.7	2.001	0.613
0.8	2.020	0.768
0.9	2.030	0.909
1.0	2.035	1.135

Sample	O.D at 430nm
<i>Euphorbia nerifolia</i>	0.458
<i>Caralluma fimbriata</i>	0.210

O.D of Standard Solution at 500nm

Phytochemical Analysis:

Preliminary screening of *Caralluma fimbriata* and *Euphorbia neriifolia* using phytochemicals analysis. Identified the main phytochemicals, which include phenols, flavonoids, and tannins. Phenolic compounds were present in both *Euphorbia neriifolia* and *Caralluma fimbriata* species to differing degrees. Of these fractions, *Euphorbia neriifolia* had the highest phenolic content, with an optical density at 760 nm that corresponded to 2.000 mg/mL of catechol equivalent, while *Caralluma fimbriata* had 1.246 mg/mL of catechol equivalent.

The tannin content of *Euphorbia neriifolia* L and *Caralluma fimbriata* species was evaluated spectrophotometrically at 500 nm and represented as tannic acid equivalents, with values of 0.129 and 0.065 mg/mL, respectively, using the Folin-Denis method. Phenols oxidise the Folin-Denis reagent, which is a combination of phosphotungstic and phosphomolybdic acids, to a blue tungsten oxide (Snell and Snell, 1937). *Caralluma fimbriata* had the lowest tannin concentration, whilst *E. neriifolia* had the highest.

The colorimetric method with aluminium chloride was used to quantify flavonoids. According to spectrophotometric measurements at 430 nm, *E. neriifolia* had a higher flavonoid content than *Caralluma fimbriata*, with a content of 0.458 mg/ml, or 100 mg of rutin, while *Caralluma fimbriata* had a lower flavonoid content of 0.210 mg/ml, or 100 mg of rutin.

Conclusion:

The findings showed that different concentrations of phenols, flavonoids, and tannins

were found in the chosen species. Of all the phytochemicals assessed, *Euphorbia neriifolia* showed the highest amounts of all secondary metabolites. Future research should concentrate on a more thorough examination of secondary metabolites using cutting-edge methods like High-Resolution Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (HR-LC-MS) and Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS).

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